

Job stress mediate: Workload on performance

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Abstract

This study aims to analyse the effect of workload on employee performance mediated by Job Stress at PT Telkom Access Denpasar. The data collection techniques used in this study used questionnaires, observations and interviews. The sampling used in this study was purposive sampling, which is a data collection technique with certain considerations. The sample used in this study was 112 employees of PT Telkom Access Denpasar. The data collection process uses a questionnaire with answers measured on a Likert scale. Data analysis used in this study using descriptive data analysis and inferential statistical analysis. The analysis technique in this study used the PLS 3.3.9 (Partial Least Square) analysis technique. The results showed that workload has a negative and significant effect on performance. Workload has a positive and significant effect on job Stress. Job Stress has a negative effect on performance and workload has a negative effect on performance mediated by Job Stress. The theoretical implications explain that the results of the study support the main theory underlying this research, namely Job Stress theory.

Keywords: Workload; Job Stress; Employee; Performance

1. Introduction

One of the factors affecting performance is workload. The term workload is often interpreted as something that is burdensome or Stressful for a person's life. Workload according to Rizky (2018) is a task given to employees to be carried out at a certain time using the skills and potential of labour which can be further divided into 2 categories of quantitative workload and quality workload. Workload can be further divided into workload that occurs due to overload, which is the amount of work that must be completed with a much shorter completion time than before. As for workload due to quality overload, where individuals who feel unable to do or complete their duties because their work requires higher abilities. This is in line with the research of Putri and Rahyuda (2019) which states that workload has a significant negative effect on the performance of Bharata Sport and Fashion employees. The results of this finding indicate that an increase in workload can cause a decrease in employee performance. However, in Rochman and Ichsan's research (2021) it is explained that workload has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This means that if employee workload increases, employee performance will also increase.

Spagnoli (2020) explains that workload is a common job demand that refers to an excessive amount of work that must be done in too little time and has been shown to have both negative and positive effects on performance. On the one hand, workload can be considered a threatening Stressor with adverse effects on performance because it can overwhelm employees who may not have sufficient resources (for example, time) to complete the job.

Suma'mur (2018: 73) explains that workload is not only a physical and mental burden but a social burden. Individuals' ability to load varies according to their capacity. Increasing workload causes a person's time to work without experiencing fatigue or interference to be shorter. Destiani (2020) defines workload as a common task performed by employees either individually or in teams during a period. In Shabbir & Naqvi's research (2017) workload and work

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complexity have a positive and significant impact on job Stress, while job Stress has a negative impact on job performance.

In addition to workload, another factor that can affect employee performance is Job Stress. Job Stress is a general term that refers to the pressures and problems experienced by everyone in their working life. This concept of Job Stress contains two meanings, namely positive and negative. If someone can manage or manage their Stress well then psychologically the Stress will foster enthusiasm and motivation to work. Conversely, if the Stress is too excessive, it can interfere with the health of an employee, both physically and non-physically. Haryati et. al. (2019) explain that Job Stress is a condition created by physical and psychological imbalances that affect the emotions and condition of an employee, so they often become angry, sensitive, unable to calm down, and difficult to cooperate. There are two factors that cause Job Stress, namely work environment factors and personal factors.

Pandey (2020) in his research explains that Job Stress is a condition in which employees are required to fulfil tasks that exceed the employee's ability and also the resources needed to carry out their duties, where there is a large difference between the reward and the demand to fulfil the task. Stress can result in decreased overall employee performance, high error rates and poor quality of work and work absenteeism due to health problems such as anxiety, unbalanced work life, depression and other types of illness. Ehsan (2019) in his research defines that Stress can be interpreted as Job Stress pressure which can be used as a refusal to come to work and a feeling of continuous pressure. Job Stress is a physical and emotional action that occurs when there is a gap between job requirements, abilities and resources. Stress is also said to be a universal element which means that employees will definitely face Stress in their life journey.

Kasim (2016) states that Job Stress negatively affects employee performance, because excessive workload, career development, family problems and organisational problems can reduce employee performance where employees feel tired, restless, unhappy, headaches, weak and irritable. However, research conducted by Zafar et al. (2015) stated the opposite to this study, with the results stating that there is a significant positive relationship between job Stress and employee performance.

Excessive Job Stress can affect employee health in a company. If employees are in an unhealthy condition, both physically and non-physically, then it can affect the performance of these employees. If employee performance decreases or is not as effective as before, the company's productivity will decrease as well. Therefore, it is hoped that the performance of employees in a company should not decrease. This can be done by reducing the negative effects of Job Stress.

2. Literature review and hypothesis development

Rochman and Ichsan (2021) found that workload has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Honda Daya Anugrah Mandiri, Sukabumi branch. This means that if employee workload increases, employee performance will also increase. Janib et al. (2021) in their research found that workload is negatively related to the performance of university academic staff in Malaysia. In Bruggen's research (2015) found that workload has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This is made clear by the fact that different levels of workload can affect employee performance, and rightly so. Chandra and Adriansyah (2017) explain the results of their research where workload has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance at PT Mega Auto Central Finance Branch in Langsa.

Hastutiningsih (2018) entitled the effect of workload and work environment on performance mediated by Job Stress (Study at PT. MSV Pictures Yogyakarta) states that workload has a negative and significant effect on the performance of employees of PT. MSV Pictures Yogyakarta. Paramitadewi (2017) in her research found that workload has a negative and significant effect on employee performance at the Tabanan Regency Regional Government Secretariat. This means that the lower the employee's workload, the more employee performance will increase.

H1 : Workload has a negative and significant effect on employee performance.

Abdullah (2015) workload and work environment simultaneously have a significant effect on Job Stress. Denizia (2018) workload has a positive and significant effect on Job Stress on employees of the East Java Provincial Social Service Surabaya. Increasing workload will also increase the Job Stress of employees of the East Java provincial social service, Surabaya. In the research of Fitriantini et. al. (2020), based on the results of statistical analysis, the perceived workload is in the high (heavy) category and the results show that workload has a significant effect on Job Stress, where the direction of the relationship is positive. The study explained that if the workload felt by an employee is high or heavy, the employee will tend to experience Stress at work.

Research by Suarhana and Riana (2016) explains that workload has a positive and significant effect on job Stress. Puspitasari and Kustanti's research (2018) found that workload has a positive and significant effect on job Stress.

H2 : Workload has a positive and significant effect on Job Stress

Rachel (2018) on the results of research and discussion that has been done, it is known that the Job Stress variable affects the employee performance variable. This research means that it supports the hypothesis proposed that Job Stress affects Employee Performance at the Manado IT Centre Management Office. Shabbir & Naqvi (2017) in their research results explain that Job Stress has a negative impact on job performance at Travel Agencies in Rawalpindi, Islamabad and AJK. Riandy (2016) in his research "The Effect of Job Stress on Employee Performance" explains that there is a significant influence between job Stress on employee performance at PT Borneo Laboratory Inspection and Surveyor Service in Samarinda.

Tri Wartono (2017) explains the results of his research that there is a significant influence between job Stress on employee performance at Mother and Baby Magazine. Sandiarta and Suwandana (2020) explain that Job Stress has a negative effect on Employee Performance at Graha Canti Cooperative. This shows that if Job Stress at Graha Canti Cooperative increases, Employee Performance at Graha Canti Cooperative will decrease. Vijayan (2018) explains that Job Stress has a significant impact on employee performance. The results of the study revealed that both male and female employees experience Job Stress in their workplace. The majority of employees in all age groups are of the opinion that Job Stress affects their performance. Ehsan (2019) in his research obtained results where Job Stress had a negative and significant effect on employee performance in the Faisalabad Banking Sector, Pakistan.

H3 : Job Stress has a negative and significant effect on employee performance

Shabbir & Naqvi (2017) in their research on the results of the effect of workload and work complexity on employee performance, with the mediating role of Job Stress and the moderate effect of social support involving 285 employees working in travel agencies located in Rawalpindi, Islamabad and AJK. The results showed that workload and job complexity have a positive and significant impact on job Stress, while job Stress has a negative impact on job performance. Whereas workload, job complexity and work pressure are consequently negatively affected by social support.

Putri and Rahyuda (2019) explained that Job Stress is a variable that is able to mediate the effect of workload on employee performance at Bharata Sport and Fashion. This result also means that workload has an indirect effect on employee performance through Job Stress. Previous tests show that workload has a positive effect on job Stress and a negative effect on employee performance. Based on these results, it can be concluded that Job Stress mediates the effect of workload on employee performance. In the research of Anisah, Imelda and Chairunnisa (2021), it was found that Job Stress did not mediate the effect of workload on employee performance at PTPN IV Medan.

Pramesthi et. al (2020) in their research results show that Job Stress has a positive effect and can mediate the effect of workload on the performance of civil servants of the Office of Cooperatives, Small and Medium Enterprises of Yogyakarta Special Region Province. This result also means that workload has an indirect effect on employee performance through Job Stress. Azizah's research (2018) in the results of her research states that workload has a negative and significant effect on employee performance through Job Stress at Bank BRI Purworejo. This means that if an employee experiences Job Stress, performance will decrease. In Hastutiningsih's research (2018) states that workload on performance through Job Stress has a negative and significant effect on the performance of employees of PT MSV Pictures Yogyakarta.

H4 : Job Stress mediates the effect of workload on employee performance.

3. Material and method

The total population of employees of PT Telkom Access Denpasar is 112 people. The sample is the object or subject of research selected to represent the entire population. This study uses purposive sampling technique. The criteria used in this study are men and women who are productive age, namely 20-60 years and have worked for at least 1 year. The sample in this study used the entire population of the company with a total of 112 employees of PT Telkom Access Denpasar Area. Data was collected using a questionnaire with a Likert scale of 1-5. To test the hypothesis and produce a model that is feasible (fit), this study uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with a variance-based or component-based approach with Partial Least Square (PLS).

4. Result and discussion

4.1. Convergent Validity

Table 1 Outer Loading

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)
X1.1 <- Workload(X)	0.887	37.888
X1.2 <- Workload(X)	0.930	61.072
X1.3 <- Workload(X)	0.902	49.986
X1.4 <- Workload(X)	0.869	31.885
X1.5 <- Workload(X)	0.879	39.641
X1.6 <- Workload(X)	0.907	46.017
X1.7 <- Workload(X)	0.853	29.983
X1.8 <- Workload(X)	0.859	32.026
Y1.1 <- Performance (Y)	0.927	62.681
Y1.2 <- Performance (Y)	0.910	50.185
Y1.3 <- Performance (Y)	0.845	35.776
Y1.4 <- Performance (Y)	0.912	47.456
Y1.5 <- Performance (Y)	0.933	67.760
Y1.6 <- Performance (Y)	0.858	34.947
Y1.7 <- Performance (Y)	0.876	36.518
Y1.8 <- Performance (Y)	0.890	46.255
Z1.1 <- Job Stress (Z)	0.878	31.417
Z1.2 <- Job Stress (Z)	0.877	37.651
Z1.3 <- Job Stress (Z)	0.868	34.808
Z1.4 <- Job Stress (Z)	0.886	43.993
Z1.5 <- Job Stress (Z)	0.873	37.043

Primary Data, 2023

Based on Table 1, it shows that all indicators already have an outer loading value of more than 0.5 (> 0.5). This shows that all indicators that have an outer loading of more than 0.5 are valid indicators.

4.2. Discriminant validity

Table 2 Cross Loading

	Workload(X)	Performance (Y)	Job Stress (Z)
X1.1	0.887	-0.779	0.715
X1.2	0.930	-0.862	0.814
X1.3	0.902	-0.821	0.790
X1.4	0.869	-0.741	0.739
X1.5	0.879	-0.840	0.747

X1.6	0.907	-0.822	0.799
X1.7	0.853	-0.773	0.728
X1.8	0.859	-0.733	0.682
Y1.1	-0.837	0.927	-0.840
Y1.2	-0.826	0.910	-0.847
Y1.3	-0.770	0.845	-0.766
Y1.4	-0.826	0.912	-0.833
Y1.5	-0.854	0.933	-0.850
Y1.6	-0.758	0.858	-0.769
Y1.7	-0.768	0.876	-0.798
Y1.8	-0.796	0.890	-0.769
Z1.1	0.705	-0.782	0.878
Z1.2	0.778	-0.810	0.877
Z1.3	0.728	-0.802	0.868
Z1.4	0.811	-0.795	0.886
Z1.5	0.695	-0.778	0.873

Primary Data, 2023

Based on Table 2, the cross loading obtained by each latent variable is higher than the other latent variables so that it can be said that the latent variables have met discriminant validity, it can be seen that the Workload (X) variable has a higher indicator than the correlation with the indicator with the Job Stress (Z) and Performance (Y) variables. the correlation of the Performance (Y) variable has a higher indicator than the correlation with the indicator with the Job Stress (Z) and Workload (X) variables. The correlation of the Job Stress (Z) variable has a higher indicator than the correlation with the indicator with the Workload (X) and Performance (Y) variables.

Another model for assessing discriminant validity is to compare the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each variable with the correlation between variables with other variables in the model. The model has good discriminant validity if the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) measurement value is more than 0.50. The results of discriminant validity testing are presented in the model as shown in Table 5.8.

Table 3 Comparison of Square Root of Average Variance Extracted with Latent Variable Correlation

	AVE	Workload(X)	Performance (Y)	Job Stress (Z)
Workload(X)	0.785	1.000	-0.900	0.850
Performance (Y)	0.800	-0.900	1.000	-0.905
Job Stress (Z)	0.768	0.850	-0.905	1.000

Primary Data, 2023

Based on Table 3, it can be explained that all variables have an AVE value above 0.50, and the correlation value for each variable is higher than the correlation between variables. These results indicate that the latent variable indicators themselves are better than the indicators of other latent variables. Based on the results of this analysis, it can be said that the data has good discriminant validity.

4.3. Composite Reliability

Table 4 Composite Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Workload(X1)	0.961	0.967
Performance (Y1)	0.964	0.970
Job Stress (Z1)	0.925	0.943

Primary Data, 2023

Based on Table 4 shows that, the composite reliability value and Cronbach's alpha value for all constructs have a value of more than 0.7. Thus in the research model, each research construct fulfils good reliability.

4.4. R-Square (R²)

Table 5 R-square

	R Square
Performance (Y1)	0.881
Job Stress (Z1)	0.722

Primary Data, 2023

In Table 5, the R-square value of the Performance variable is 0.881, and Job Stress is 0.722. This value will later be used to calculate how good the Q-square predictive relevance is, which is used to measure how well the observations produced by the model and also the parameter estimates. A Q-square value > 0 indicates the model has predictive relevance. Based on Table 5, the predictive relevance value (Q²) is calculated, namely:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q^2 &= 1 - (1 - R1^2) (1 - R2^2) \\
 &= 1 - (1 - 0.881) (1 - 0.722) \\
 &= 1 - (0.119) (0.278) \\
 &= 1 - 0.033 \\
 &= 0.967
 \end{aligned}$$

The Q² Predictive Relevance value of 0.002 indicates that the model is weak, 0.15 indicates a moderate model and 0.35 indicates that the model is strong. The results of this calculation show that the Q² value is 0.967, this value is greater than 0. So it can be interpreted that the model is good because it has a relevant predictive, which is 96.7 percent. This shows that the variation in the Performance variable can be explained by the variables used, namely Workload and Job Stress, while 3.3 per cent is explained by other variables that have not been included in the research model.

4.5. Direct Effect

Table 6 Path Coefficients (Direct Effect)

Construct	Path Coefficient	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Workload(X) -> Performance (Y)	-0.470	2.835	0.005
Workload(X) -> Job Stress (Z)	0.850	18.274	0.000
Job Stress (Z) -> Performance (Y)	-0.506	2.957	0.003

Primary Data, 2023

Table 6 shows that Workload has a negative and significant effect on Performance with a path coefficient value of -0.470 and a p-value of 0.005 or <0.05 and t-statistics are > 1.96 then (H1) is accepted. This shows that the higher the Workload, the more the Performance of employees of PT Telkom Access Denpasar decreases.

Workload has a positive and significant influence on Job Stress with a path coefficient value of 0.850 and a p-value of 0.000 or <0.05 and t-statistics are > 1.96 then (H2) is accepted. This shows that the higher the Workload obtained by employees, the higher the level of Job Stress felt by employees of PT Telkom Access Denpasar.

Job Stress has a negative and significant effect on Performance with a path coefficient value of -0.506 p-value of 0.003 or <0.05 and t-statistics are > 1.96 then (H3) is accepted. This shows that the higher the Job Stress felt by employees, the lower the performance of employees of PT Telkom Access Denpasar.

4.6. Indirect Effect

Table 7 Indirect Effect

Indirect Effect	Effect			Result
	P1	P2	P3	
Workload(X) -> Job Stress (Z) -> Performance (Y)	0.000 (Sig.)	0.003 (Sig.)	0.005 (Sig.)	Partial Mediation

Primary Data, 2023; Description: significance (Sig.) = P-value <0.05 and t-statistic > 1.96; P1 = Direct effect of exogenous variables (X) on mediating variables (Z); P2 = Direct effect of mediating variable (Z) on endogenous variable (Y); P3 = Direct effect of exogenous variables (X) on endogenous variables (Y)

Job Stress can mediate the effect of Workload on Performance. This can be seen from several indicators such as I am clear with information from the company about my role or position at the Institute, my job has no great pressure and does not demand much of me and the work I do is not monotonous. These results are shown by looking at the results of testing the indirect effect of Workload on Performance by involving Job Stress variables getting significant results. Then, the direct effect of Workload on Performance gets significant results, and the direct effect of Job Stress on Performance also gets significant results. So, Job Stress can mediate competitive partial mediation or complementary mediation on the effect of Workload on Performance. Based on these results it can be concluded that the higher the Workload of employees, it can increase employee Job Stress, so that in the end the performance of employees of PT Telkom Access Denpasar will increase.

5. Conclusion

workload has a negative and significant effect on performance, workload has a positive and significant effect on Job Stress, Job Stress has a negative and significant effect on performance and Job Stress can act as a mediator in the effect of workload on performance.

These results support the main theory underlying this research, namely Job Stress theory. This theory explains that how work can cause stress or pressure to employees in a company. Employees can interpret it as a perceived discomfort triggered by events, events or situations that are too intense and frequent to exceed a person's or human resources' ability to handle them. In this Job Stress theory, it is also explained that it can be triggered by work conditions, employee anxiety about their work environment, employee work and responses that are not in accordance with employee expectations. Excessive workload can put pressure on employees and this will be a trigger for Job Stress. Stress can also trigger tension reactions that can have a negative or positive impact.

The results of this study resulted in two practical implications which can be explained as follows; First, Job Stress has an influence in affecting performance compared to workload. This shows from the behaviour of employees who experience stress about their work because they want to be free from thoughts about their work. With the task demands and role demands given to employees of PT Telkom Akses Denpasar, the performance of these employees will experience Job Stress.

Second, workload also really needs to be considered by PT Telkom Akses Denpasar because workload also affects employee performance. It is hoped that the company can manage and regulate the portion and standard of work that

will be given to its employees. Employees can have the perception that if the workload given by the company amounts to more than their abilities, it can be a trigger for a decrease in employee performance or employee Job Stress.

Compliance with ethical standards

Statement of informed consent

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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